

Problems and Opportunities of Digital Finance for Financial Inclusion and Innovation in Uzbekistan

Fazilat Goyibnazarova Salim qizi

Student of Oxford Brookes University,

MSc International Business Management and Digital Strategy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11001911>

Abstract. *Digital finance offers excellent opportunities to promote financial inclusion and drive innovation in Uzbekistan. However, there are several obstacles to its widespread adoption and effectiveness. This article assesses the current state of digital finance in Uzbekistan, highlights priority issues and examines prospects for promoting financial inclusion and innovation. By examining regulatory structures, infrastructure expansion, and socio-economic elements, this study provides perspectives on strategies for using digital finance to combat financial marginalization and promote economic progress in Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *Digital finance, Financial inclusion, Innovation, Regulatory environment, Technological infrastructure, Socio-economic factors, Uzbekistan.*

Introduction.

It has been 24 years since the 21st century, the technological century, became people's way of life. Currently, the century has lived up to its name. It is undeniable that digital technology is advancing in every system today. In recent years, these digital technologies have shown several innovations to the public to facilitate the financial services of the state and have achieved the name of digital finance. Digital finance, encompassing mobile money, electronic payments, and other financial services delivered through digital channels, has emerged as a powerful tool for advancing financial inclusion and innovation globally. In Uzbekistan, a country with a growing economy and a large population, digital finance presents significant opportunities to expand access to financial services, promote economic development, and improve livelihoods. Digital finance, including mobile banking, online payments and various electronic financial services, is revolutionizing the financial scene in Uzbekistan and promises significant positive changes for people.

The development of digital management systems along with the flow of information makes it more efficient and productive, enabling better communication between organizations, businesses, governments and people. The ability to use and manipulate information, and the rise of human capital with cognitive skills paired with spatial, technological, and occupational changes are the key markers of an informational or network society. The public sector has not followed the non-governmental use of ICT and in recent times begun to realize the capacity of digital projects to adapt to changes in public needs, making the best use of governmental assets and, above all, provide support for more fair and participatory democracy or governance that includes all.

The most important sector of digital governance is e-government service, which includes all digital sectors. This sector increases transparency and accountability between the state and citizens. The transition to digital governance is facilitated by the presence of a transparent, accessible, and responsible government, primarily aimed at enhancing public service efficiency and fostering citizen engagement. Implementing e-government is a voluntary development process. In some cases, this may delay the need for e-government in terms of openness, accountability and public participation. On the other hand, another group called "Building a country in Transition", had to synchronize the change in the public administration process (mostly

with corruption and high performance) with digital control. The model for the emergence of digital money is the integration of electronic government, electronic governance, electronic management and electronic services. Any time a country introduces a new way of governing is considered a time of great change and change for the country. Every change has two effects, positive or negative. Some scholars have expressed scepticism about the effectiveness of e-government in autocratic or less democratic countries around the world, arguing that the digitalization of the public sector further increases the monopoly of power.

Current Landscape of Digital Finance in Uzbekistan:

The rapid development of technology has changed the financial environment around the world and led to changes in the provision of and access to financial services. This literature review examines the global digital finance landscape and suggests perspectives specific to Uzbekistan. Digital finance has seen unprecedented growth globally, driven by factors such as technological advancements, changes in consumer behaviour and regulatory administration. The global financial sector is using digitalization to increase efficiency, reduce costs and expand accounting. The emergence of blockchain, artificial intelligence and mobile technologies has created new financial solutions, laid the foundation for decentralized finance (DeFi) and changed the traditional business paradigm. These innovations affect both developed and emerging markets. These developments are also a reason to look at history. The historical situation of digital finance in Uzbekistan has undergone significant developments in recent years. Traditionally, the country's financial environment has relied on traditional banking services. However, digital finance is gaining more attention as the government encourages innovation and financial inclusion. Uzbekistan has made significant progress in digital finance in recent years. The government has implemented policies to promote financial digitalization and increase access to digital payments. Mobile operators and financial institutions work together to provide mobile money services that allow people to do business, pay bills and easily access financial services on their mobile phones. Initiatives such as the launch of the National Interbank Transaction Center (NIPC) and mobile banking services have borne fruit. It plays an important role in the development of digital finance. Additionally, regulatory reforms, including the introduction of electronic payments and the promotion of fintech innovation, have further encouraged the development of digital finance in Uzbekistan. Digital finance plays an important role in promoting financial inclusion, especially in emerging economies like Uzbekistan. Mobile banking and digital payment platforms have the potential to reduce access to financial disparities and empower the unbanked. However, despite these improvements, the penetration of digital financial services in Uzbekistan remains low. Many people, especially in rural and underserved communities, still lack access to banking services and experience difficulty using these services. Solve digital financial problems. Additionally, restrictions on the use of digital tools, low levels of financial literacy and regulatory constraints make it difficult to develop a digital economy in the country.

Challenges in Uzbekistan's Digital Finance: Infrastructure, Literacy, Regulation, Security, and Cultural Barriers:

According to the analysis of the literature, the process of adapting the digital financial system of Uzbekistan is facing various difficulties. Challenges facing digital finance in Uzbekistan include infrastructure, literacy, regulation, security, and cultural barriers.

The literature on digital finance highlights its potential to aid consumption and economic development. However, in Uzbekistan, problems such as low financial inclusion and complex

application procedures prevent its adoption. The digital financial management system in Uzbekistan needs to be further developed to support innovation and ensure consumer protection. Regulatory confusion and cumbersome licensing and compliance processes limit business opportunities and hinder the growth of digital financial services. Clear and transparent guidelines are essential to foster trust among stakeholders and facilitate the expansion of digital finance. Despite these problems, the country has achieved digital transformation that can solve some of these problems.

At the same time, Uzbekistan faces infrastructure challenges, including poor internet access and insufficient digital infrastructure in rural areas. Lack of efficient connectivity and electricity makes it difficult to use digital financial services, especially in remote areas where banking facilities are difficult to access. Investments in broadband infrastructure and efforts to improve connectivity are key to increasing digital spending across the country.

It is also clear that there is a need for financial literacy programs that will enable users to understand the risks and benefits of these services. The low level of financial literacy and financial literacy hinders the support of digital financial services by the Uzbek population. Many people lack the knowledge and skills to properly use the digital payment platform, leading to inefficiency and distrust of digital financial solutions. Financial education programs aimed at a diverse target population are needed to increase financial knowledge and encourage the adoption of digital financial services. Especially, working with a generalized database requires strong security, which is the responsibility of the state. Security issues such as cyber threats and data breaches require strong measures to build trust among users and encourage the use of digital financial services.

A lack of financial literacy paves the way for emerging crimes against the industry. Cultural barriers further complicate the adoption process and emphasize the need for tailored approaches that take into account local preferences and practices. Effective regulatory frameworks are essential to harness the benefits of digital finance while mitigating associated risks. Striking a balance between fostering innovation and ensuring consumer protection is a key challenge faced by regulators globally.

Opportunities for Digital Finance in Uzbekistan:

Success in digital finance hinges on several key factors, including financial inclusion, operational efficiency, technological advancements, and government initiatives. Achieving financial inclusion through digital means has become a global priority. Despite the difficulties, success in digital finance is evident in Uzbekistan. Increased financial inclusion, improved efficiency, technological advancements and government initiatives have yielded positive results.

Government initiatives such as introducing personal systems and promoting digital commerce will play an important role in adoption. Technological advances such as artificial intelligence and blockchain are further increasing the efficiency and convenience of digital finance by helping to create new financial products and services. Uzbekistan has the potential to transform its financial ecosystem using new technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence and digital systems. By embracing innovation and investing in technology, Uzbekistan can move beyond the corporate economy model and become more inclusive, providing citizens and businesses with more income and potential.

Public-private partnerships and collaboration between government agencies, financial institutions and technology companies can support the expansion of digital finance in Uzbekistan. Stakeholders can leverage each other's strengths and expertise to create new solutions, improve

services, and improve access to financial services for underserved people. Government initiatives, such as the National Program for the Development of the Digital Economy, aim to leverage digital technologies to enhance financial services accessibility.

In general, Uzbekistan's journey towards mastering digital finance is characterized by a combination of challenges and successes. Infrastructure, literacy, regulatory, security and cultural barriers need to be overcome for sustainable growth of digital finance in the region. Government initiatives, technological innovations and successful case studies provide a roadmap for developing an inclusive and efficient digital financial ecosystem in Uzbekistan. However, it can be assumed that the research studied so far is not enough. Incorporating technology into the financial system and adapting it is not an easy and narrow task, many of the data we reviewed have the same content, but they did not propose a new part or a new business strategy.

Conclusion:

Digital finance provides an effective way to promote financial inclusion and economic development in Uzbekistan. Resolving administrative issues, strengthening the digital system and promoting financial literacy are important steps to unlock the potential of digital finance in the country. By seizing opportunities for cooperation, innovation and technology, Uzbekistan can pave the way for a more viable and profitable economy for all citizens

References:

1. Tapscott, D. and Agnew, D. 1999. Governance in the digital economy. Finance and Development.
2. Khodjaev. 2004. E-Government implementation and administrative reform in Uzbekistan – interrelations and interference. UNDP Digital Development Initiative Programme (UNDP DDI) and Center for Economic Research (CER)
3. Ndou, D. 2004a. e-Government for developing countries: Opportunities and challenges. EJISDC The Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries.
4. World Bank. (2018). Global Findex Database 2017: Measuring Financial Inclusion and the Fintech Revolution. World Bank.
5. Mansurov, P., (2021). Development Prospects For Digital Economy Development in Uzbekistan.
6. Davletova, D., (2022). Digital Transformation Process in the Private and the Public sectors in Uzbekistan.
7. Blockchain Association of Uzbekistan. (2023). "Blockchain Technology and Its Impact on Financial Inclusion in Uzbekistan."
8. Ministry of Finance, Uzbekistan. (2022). "National Strategy for Digital Finance Development."
9. United Nations Capital Development Fund. (2023). Digital Finance Landscape in Uzbekistan: Opportunities and Challenges.
10. International Finance Corporation. (2022). Unlocking Digital Finance Potential in Uzbekistan: Policy Recommendations.
11. Asian Development Bank. (2020). Uzbekistan: Country Partnership Strategy.
12. United Nations Capital Development Fund. (2023). Digital Finance Landscape in Uzbekistan: Opportunities and Challenges.